

1 **WHEAT PERFORMANCE WITH SUBCLOVER LIVING MULCH IN DIFFERENT**
2 **AGRO-ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS DEPENDS ON CROP MANAGEMENT**

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22 **HIGHLIGHTS**

- 23 - Grain yield of wheat was mostly reduced when intercropped with subclover
24 - Subclover as living mulch in wheat performed better in low input systems
25 - Wheat intercropped with subclover needs appropriate crop management

26

27 **ABSTRACT:**

28 Intercropping has been proposed as a useful strategy for reducing external inputs in cereal-based
29 cropping systems, while maintaining adequate levels of crop yield. Intercropping of wheat and
30 subclover (*Trifolium subterraneum* L.), implemented as living mulch, is recommended, but there is
31 limited experimental proof for its suitability in different environments. The main objective of this
32 study was to provide an overview and evaluation of wheat-subclover intercropping under different
33 agro-environmental conditions. Coordinated field experiments were conducted over a two-year
34 period in six sites located in four agro-environmental zones: Atlantic North (Neu-Eichenberg,
35 Germany), Continental (Freising, Germany – Tänikon, Switzerland), Mediterranean North (Viterbo,
36 Italy), Mediterranean South (Sidi Alla Tazi and Sidi El Aidi, Morocco). Wheat–subclover
37 intercropping was compared with a pure wheat. Additionally, the other treatments adopted in
38 specific sites were: soil tillage (conventional and minimum tillage); nitrogen fertilization (high and

39 low level); compost application (with and without), cropping system (conventional and organic).
40 The measurements recorded were: soil coverage, wheat and subclover phenological stages, wheat
41 grain yield and yield components, subclover and weed biomass. The data of each site were analyzed
42 separately and were also used for a meta-analysis in order to obtain an overview of how pedo-
43 climatic conditions affect the interactions of subclover living mulch with wheat and weeds. Overall,
44 wheat-subclover intercropping reduced weed infestation at most sites (from 22 to 75%).
45 Intercropping also resulted in grain yield losses (from 1 to 18%) compared to pure wheat. In agro-
46 environmental zones where subclover growth was limited by cold temperatures (Atlantic North) or
47 dry conditions (Mediterranean South), hardly any grain yield reduction of intercropped wheat was
48 observed. In contrast, intercropping significantly reduced wheat grain yield at the sites where
49 subclover developed properly (Mediterranean North) probably because of the competition between
50 the species. Subclover biomass and wheat grain yield were also negatively correlated and yield
51 reductions were generally due to a reduced number of fertile spikes. The yield gap between
52 intercropped and pure wheat was reduced when: (i) wheat seed density was similar in intercropped
53 and pure wheat; (ii) there was a proper spatial arrangement of subclover and wheat; (iii) the amount
54 of added mineral nitrogen fertilizer was reduced, while compost application did not influence the
55 cropping systems. The use of subclover living mulch in wheat appears to be most suitable for low
56 input systems. Future research should focus on the development of appropriate crop management
57 practices for intercropping in order to avoid wheat yield loss.

58

59 **KEY WORDS:** Cereal – legume intercropping; Wheat grain yield; Weeds; Cropping system;
60 Nitrogen fertilization.

61

62 **INTRODUCTION**

63 The simplification of cropping systems over the last decades has been accompanied worldwide by
64 an increased use of chemical fertilizers, pesticides, and heavier mechanization. These practices have
65 produced higher crop yields, yet they have simultaneously contributed to an increase of
66 environmental issues, such as soil erosion and water contamination (Nazari et al., 2015).
67 Consequently, it is necessary to design innovative cropping systems for greater nutrient use
68 efficiency and resource conservation, which are more sustainable from an environmental point of
69 view. Importantly, agro-ecosystems should be more diversified by increasing the number of species
70 grown and using more leguminous crops (Bedoussac and Justes, 2011) or including cover crops
71 (Wittwer et al., 2017). The adoption of intercropping could be a useful strategy for reducing
72 external inputs while maintaining adequate levels of crop yield (Tilman et al., 2002).

73 Intercropping is defined as the co-cultivation of two or more species in the same space and for a
74 significant part of their growing season, without necessarily being sown and harvested together. An
75 established cover crop intercropped and grown simultaneously with an annual cash crop is known
76 as living mulch (Hartwig and Ammon, 2002). The benefits of using living mulch as cropping
77 systems include a reduction of water runoff and soil erosion, and the suppression of weed
78 germination and weed establishment through competition for limited resources and/or the
79 production of allelochemicals (Costanzo and Barberi, 2014). However, competition with the main
80 crop for limited resources such as water, light and nutrients should be minimal (Hiltbrunner et al.,
81 2007). This can be achieved when the intercropped species occupy different niches in time and
82 space (Malézieux et al., 2009) using complementary resources (Bedoussac and Justes, 2010). Using
83 a legume living mulch in an intercropped cereal system increases biodiversity and could reduce the
84 need of external inputs such as nitrogen (N) fertilizers, herbicides and pesticides, thus improving the
85 sustainability of the cropping system (Bedoussac and Justes, 2010).

86 Subclover (*Trifolium subterraneum* L.) is an annual legume with prostrate and non-rooting stems
87 that adapts well to mild winters during which its vegetative growth and part of the reproductive
88 phenophase occurs. Seeds buried naturally in the soil in the spring remain dormant until high
89 summer temperatures drop and rainfall or irrigation occurs in the autumn. Since the plants die due
90 to the increase in temperatures in late spring, it is not necessary to suppress subclover mechanically
91 or chemically. Therefore, due to its particular life-cycle subclover seems to meet the requirements
92 of a successful living mulch during the cereal crop cycle and an efficient dead mulch after wheat
93 grain harvest during the summer period (Campiglia et al. 2014). Furthermore, its natural re-
94 establishment ensures a new legume cover crop free of charge in the following period which can be
95 used as cover crop or dead mulch for cultivating vegetable crops, such as tomato, pepper and
96 eggplant under no-tillage conditions (Campiglia et al., 2014 and 2010). Therefore, using subclover
97 as living mulch in wheat appears to be a suitable option for reducing the external inputs and costs of
98 agricultural production. Moreover, living mulches are compatible with both organic and
99 conservation agricultural systems (Canali et al., 2017). However, as yet few studies have evaluated
100 the effects of subclover–wheat intercropping systems. Hence, it is necessary to determine if the
101 wheat-subclover intercropping system works in selected agro-environmental conditions to provide
102 benefits, before it can be recommended as a agricultural practice. We hypothesized that using
103 subclover as living mulch in a wheat–subclover intercropping systems is feasible in several agro-
104 environmental conditions and could be an environment-friendly management practice that has
105 beneficial effects on the agro-ecosystem. The main objective of this study was to provide an
106 overview and evaluation of subclover used as living mulch in wheat under a wide range of pedo-

107 climatic conditions spanning from the Atlantic North to the Mediterranean South. A total of 14
108 coordinated two-year field trials in seven sites were evaluated. The specific aims of the study were:
109 (i) to assess subclover living mulch performance; (ii) to evaluate the effects of subclover living
110 mulch on yield and yield components of wheat; (iii) to determine the ability of wheat-subclover
111 intercropping to suppress weeds.

112

113 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

114 *Site characteristics, crop management and experimental design*

115 Wheat–subclover intercropping experiments were carried out over two growing seasons across a
116 vast area (from 51°22' to 33°07' N and from 6°22' to 12°04' E) in seven sites located in four agro-
117 environmental zones as defined by Jongman et al. (2006): Atlantic North (Neu-Eichenberg,
118 Germany), Continental [Freising, Germany (2 sites) and Tänikon, Switzerland)], Mediterranean
119 North (Viterbo, Italy), Mediterranean South (Sidi Alla Tazi and Sidi El Aidi, Morocco) (Fig. 1,
120 Table 1). At each site, the experiment was performed twice, in 2012/13 and in 2013/14, resulting in
121 a total of 14 site-year combinations. Wheat cultivars were selected to match the agro-environmental
122 conditions of each site, while the subclover cultivar (Campeda) was the same in all sites. The
123 cultivar Campeda belongs to subsp. *subterraneum* of subterranean clover native of Sardinia island
124 in Mediterranean basin (Piano et al., 1997) and released as cultivars in Australia (Nichols et al.,
125 2009). According to Nichols et al. (2013), Campeda cultivar shows a growth habit semi-erect and
126 limited height. This cultivar is characterized of medium flowering class and a high level of residual
127 hardseededness (about 30%), which contribute to its good persistence even in agro-environmental
128 conditions featuring moderately severe spring-summer stress. Campeda forms very thick and dense
129 swards, also owing to its outstanding seed yield. Agronomic practices and plant protection measures
130 were carried out at appropriate times at the given sites following regional recommendations.

131 At Neu-Eichenberg, the field experiments were carried out at the organic experimental farm of
132 Kassel University (hereafter called KU), in two adjacent fields previously cropped with grass-clover
133 for two years. The soil in the experimental area is classified as *Haplic Luvisol* (Soil Survey Staff,
134 2009). Experimental factors were (i) tillage: either prior to winter wheat sowing inversion tillage
135 with a moldboard plough at a depth of 25 cm, followed by seed bed preparation with disk harrow
136 (hereafter called conventional tillage) or non-inversion tillage using a chisel plough at a depth of 10
137 cm, followed by seed bed preparation with a disk harrow in the first year, while in the second year
138 the seed bed preparation was performed by direct drilling of wheat and subclover living mulch after
139 undercutting the grass-clover pre-crop once (hereafter called minimum tillage); (ii) cropping
140 system: pure winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L., cv. Achat) and wheat-subclover intercropping;

141 (iii) organic fertilization: application of yard waste compost at a rate of 5 t dry matter ha⁻¹ (hereafter
142 called WC+) and no application of yard waste compost (hereafter called WC-). The distance
143 between the wheat rows was 30 cm in both pure and intercropped treatments. Wheat plant density
144 was 350 seeds m⁻² in both cropping systems, while subclover was sown at a density of 300 seeds m⁻².
145 The weeds were left to grow undisturbed except in the first experimental year where they were
146 controlled via hoeing and harrowing in spring. The experimental design was a randomized split-
147 split-plot with four replicates, with soil tillage as main plot, cropping system as sub-plot and organic
148 fertilization as sub-sub-plot. The sub-sub-plot size was 90 m² (6 m x 15 m).

149 At Freising, the field experiments were carried out on two experimental farms of the Technical
150 University of Munich (hereafter called TUM) that are located 4 km apart: the experimental farm of
151 Viehhausen, which was managed organically (hereafter called TUMorg) and the experimental farm
152 of Dürnast, managed conventionally (hereafter called TUMconv). The preceding crops were
153 soybean and faba bean in the two experiments at TUMorg, and maize in the experiments carried
154 out at TUMconv. The soil in both experimental areas is classified as *Cambisol* (Soil Survey Staff,
155 2009). The experimental factors at TUMconv were (i) cropping system: pure winter wheat
156 (*Triticum aestivum* L., cv. Achat) and wheat-subclover intercropping; (ii) nitrogen fertilization: 100
157 kg N ha⁻¹ (hereafter called N+) and 50 kg N ha⁻¹ (hereafter called N-). The N+ corresponds to the
158 farmer's normal practice, the N- fertilization level tested in this experiment represent a plausible
159 rate that could be adopted under intercropping conditions. At TUMorg, the experimental factors
160 were the same two cropping systems as in TUMconv with no fertilizer treatments. In both sites, the
161 distance between the wheat rows was 12.5 cm in pure wheat, while the intercropping pattern was 2
162 rows of wheat with a distance of 12.5 cm and a 25 cm strip of subclover between the paired wheat
163 rows. Wheat plant density was 450 and 300 seeds m⁻² in pure wheat and intercropped wheat,
164 respectively, while subclover was sown at a density of 300 seeds m⁻². The weeds were left to grow
165 undisturbed throughout both wheat cropping seasons. At TUMconv, the experimental design was a
166 randomized split-plot with four replicates, with the cropping system as main plot and the nitrogen
167 fertilization level as the sub-plot, while at TUMorg, the experiment was monofactorial, with a
168 simple randomized block design. In both sites the smallest plot size was 20 m² (10 m x 2 m).

169 At Tänikon, the field experiments were carried out at the experimental farm of Agroscope (hereafter
170 called AGS) in two fields previously cropped with forage pea. The soil in the experimental area is
171 classified as *Hapludalf* (Soil Survey Staff, 2009). The experimental factors were (i) cropping
172 system: pure winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L., cv. CH Claro) and wheat-subclover intercropping;
173 and (ii) nitrogen fertilization level: 140 kg N ha⁻¹ (hereafter called N+) and 70 kg N ha⁻¹ (hereafter
174 called N-). The N+ corresponds to the farmer's normal practice, the N- fertilization level tested in

175 this experiment represent a plausible rate that could be adopted under intercropping conditions. The
176 sowing patterns and densities were as at TUM described above. The weeds were controlled with
177 herbicide in the pure wheat treatment in spring, whereas no weed control measures were performed
178 in the intercropped treatment. The experimental design was a randomized split-plot with four
179 replicates, with the cropping system as main plot and the nitrogen fertilization as the sub-plot. The
180 smallest plot size was 48 m² (6 m x 8 m).

181 At Viterbo, the field experiments were carried out at the experimental farm of Tuscia University
182 (hereafter called UNITUS) in two fields previously kept fallow. The soil in the experimental area is
183 classified as *Typic Xerofluvent* (Soil Survey Staff, 2009). The experimental factors were (i)
184 cropping system: pure winter wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf., cv. Colosseo) and wheat-subclover
185 intercropping; and (ii) nitrogen fertilization level: 100 kg N ha⁻¹ (hereafter called N+) and 50 kg N
186 ha⁻¹ (hereafter called N-). The N+ corresponds to the farmer's normal practice, the N- fertilization
187 level tested in this experiment represent a plausible rate that could be adopted under intercropping
188 conditions. The sowing patterns and densities were as at TUM described above. The weeds were
189 left to grow undisturbed throughout both wheat cropping seasons. The experimental design was a
190 randomized split-plot with four replicates, with the cropping system as main plot and the nitrogen
191 fertilization level as the sub-plot. The smallest plot size was 48 m² (12 m x 4 m).

192 At Sidi Allal Tazi and Sidi El Aidi, the study was carried out at the experimental stations of the
193 National Institute for Agricultural Research (INRA) of Morocco by INRA and ICARDA,
194 respectively, with identical design. The soil in the experimental areas is classified as *Vertic*
195 *Calcixeroll* (Soil Survey Staff, 2009). The experimental factors were (i) cropping system: pure
196 wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L., cv. Kharouba) and wheat-subclover intercropping; and (ii) nitrogen
197 fertilization level: 100 kg N ha⁻¹ (hereafter called N+) and 50 kg N ha⁻¹ (hereafter called N-). The
198 N+ corresponds to the farmer's normal practice, the N- fertilization level tested in this experiment
199 represent a plausible rate that could be adopted under intercropping conditions. The distance
200 between wheat rows was 15 cm in the pure and intercropped system, and subclover was broadcasted
201 in the intercropped system. In both systems, the seeding rate of bread wheat was 400 seeds m⁻² and
202 subclover was sown at the density of 300 seeds m⁻². The weeds were left to grow undisturbed
203 throughout both wheat cropping seasons. At the ICARDA site, at the beginning of the second
204 growing season, the field was irrigated in order to assure uniform seed germination under dry
205 conditions. The experimental design was a randomized split-plot with four replicates, with the
206 cropping system as main plot and the nitrogen fertilization level as the sub-plot. The smallest plot
207 size was 31.5 m² (7 m x 4.5 m).

208

209 *Measurements and analysis*

210 For each site and in each year, the phenological stages of both wheat and subclover were recorded.
211 In all field experiments, ground coverage of wheat, subclover and weeds grown in each plot was
212 visually estimated at the beginning of wheat stem elongation (Brandsaeter and Netland, 1999).
213 Subclover and weed aboveground biomass were collected at subclover flowering by hand-clipping
214 the plants within a 1 m x 1 m quadrat placed randomly at the centre of each plot at the soil surface,
215 while wheat was harvested at physiological maturity. The wheat plants were cut at ground level and
216 plant height, number of fertile spikes, kernels per spike, thousand grain weight (TGW) were
217 recorded. The wheat straw was separated from the wheat grains and both fractions as well as
218 subclover and weed aboveground biomass were oven dried until constant weight in order to
219 determine the dry matter content (DM). The subclover seedlings were measured in the autumn after
220 harvesting the wheat in order to evaluate the reseeding capacity of subclover.

221

222 *Statistical analysis*

223 For each site, the data on wheat grain yield and yield components were analyzed with analyses of
224 variance (ANOVA) using JMP statistical software package version 4.0 (SAS, 1996), considering
225 the year as a repeated measure across time in all sites (Cody and Smith, 1997). At TUMconv, AGS,
226 UNITUS, INRA and ICARDA a split-plot experimental design with four replicates was used for the
227 wheat variables, where the cropping system was considered the main factor, the nitrogen
228 fertilization as split factor and the year as repeated measure. At KU a split-split-plot experimental
229 design with four replicates was adopted for analysing the wheat characteristics, where the soil
230 tillage was considered as the main factor, the cropping system as split factor, the yard waste
231 compost application as the split-split factor, and the year as repeated measure. At TUMorg a one
232 factorial analysis with four replications was performed for evaluating wheat yield and yield
233 components. Percentage data of soil cover were arcsine transformed before analysis in order to
234 homogenize the variance (Gomez and Gomez, 1984). The data shown in the results were back-
235 transformed. The effect means were compared with Fisher's protected LSD ($P < 0.05$).

236 Wheat grain yield, wheat yield components and weed aboveground biomass data of intercropped
237 wheat and pure wheat treatments were extracted from the selected field experiments as response
238 variables. The natural log of the response ratio (ln R) was used as a measure of effect size (Hedges
239 et al., 1999): $\ln R = \ln (X_{IW}/X_{PW})$, where X_{IW} and X_{PW} are the measured values of the response
240 variable under intercropped and pure wheat cropping systems, respectively. Meta-analysis was
241 performed using a non-parametric weighting function. JMP software was used to calculate mean
242 effect sizes and to generate bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for each mean effect size

243 using a bootstrapping procedure (Huang et al., 2015). In order to ease interpretation, the effect size
244 was expressed as the percentage change, which was estimated by $(R - 1) \times 100\%$. A negative
245 percentage change indicates a decrease in the response variable under intercropped plots compared
246 with pure plots, while a positive value indicates an increase. The mean percentage change was
247 considered to be significantly different from zero if the 95% CI did not overlap with zero (Hedges
248 et al., 1999). Linear regressions were performed for selected variables.

249

250 **RESULTS**

251 *Development of wheat and subclover*

252 In all sites, no significant differences were observed in the emergence of wheat between pure and
253 intercropped treatments in the two experimental years (data not shown). However, wheat
254 established one to three weeks earlier than subclover, even if both species were sown
255 simultaneously (Fig. 2). At the beginning of wheat stem elongation, the cereal crop showed a higher
256 soil coverage compared to subclover (on average 50 vs. 9 % of soil coverage, respectively, Table 2).
257 However at this stage, total soil coverage in the wheat–subclover intercrops was higher than pure
258 wheat in all sites [on average 57 (48 % wheat + 9 % subclover) vs. 49 %, respectively], with the
259 exception of ICARDA (Table 2). At UNITUS, TUM and AGS, subclover soil coverage was much
260 higher than that observed in the other sites, while wheat soil coverage intercropped with subclover
261 was lower compared to the pure wheat crop (Table 2). Where it survived, subclover flowered after
262 wheat in the northern sites, while it flowered before wheat in the Mediterranean North and
263 Mediterranean South sites (Fig. 2). Seed ripening of subclover preceded the wheat in the southern
264 agro-environmental zones (UNITUS, INRA and ICARDA) and was simultaneous with wheat in
265 Switzerland (Fig. 2).

266

267 *Subclover biomass production and its characteristics*

268 At subclover flowering, the highest amount of subclover aboveground biomass was observed at
269 UNITUS (on average over the years 229 g m⁻² of DM, Fig. 3), while at AGS and TUM, although
270 the subclover grew regularly in the early phenological stages, the amount of subclover aboveground
271 biomass at flowering stage was low (64 and 53 g DM m⁻², respectively, Fig. 3). At INRA and
272 ICARDA, the growth of the subclover living mulch was very poor (23 and 2 g DM m⁻²,
273 respectively, Fig. 3), while at KU no aboveground biomass was observed after winter.
274 Consequently the subclover seed production was variable among the agro-environmental zones. It
275 was insignificant at KU, scarce at AGS, TUM, ICARDA and INRA, while it was plentiful a

276 UNITUS where the subclover was able to regenerate abundantly in the following autumn (on
277 average 506 subclover seedlings m⁻²).

278

279 *Wheat grain yield and yield components*

280 There were few interactions among the main effects regarding the wheat grain yield and yield
281 components, therefore the analysis was focused on the main effects and two-way interactions
282 observed in the ANOVA (Table 3). Grain yields of pure wheat ranged from 5.5 t ha⁻¹ at KU to 3.2 t
283 ha⁻¹ at ICARDA, with a mean of 4.4 t ha⁻¹, while in intercropped wheat it varied from 5.4 t ha⁻¹ at
284 KU to 3.2 t ha⁻¹ at ICARDA, with an average of 4.1 t ha⁻¹ (Fig. 4). At UNITUS, TUM and AGS,
285 cereal grain yield was significantly reduced compared to pure wheat (on average -16, -10, and -18
286 %, respectively), while at KU, INRA and ICARDA there were no effects of the cropping system
287 (Fig. 4). However, considering the agro-environmental zones, in Mediterranean North and
288 Continental zones, the grain yield of intercropped wheat was significantly reduced compared to
289 pure wheat (Fig. 5a). This decrease was generally due to fewer fertile spikes (Fig. 6), even if at
290 UNITUS it was also due to the lower kernel number per spike (Fig. 4). There was a negative
291 association between the aboveground biomass production of the subclover and the change in wheat
292 grain yield (Fig. 7a).

293 Wheat grain yield was also significantly affected by N fertilization and experimental year at all sites
294 except for ICARDA site, where fertilization was not significant (Table 3). Among the experimental
295 sites, N fertilization proved to have positive effects on wheat grain yield and yield components, and
296 it only interacted with year at INRA (Table 3), while no significant changes in cereal production
297 were observed following the compost application at KU (Table 3). As expected, applying N
298 fertilization to all conventional sites after wheat tillering (Fig. 2) favored the growth of the cereal
299 both in pure and in intercropping systems. However, the effects were more consistent in pure wheat
300 than in the intercropped wheat (Fig. 5b).

301

302 *Effects of subclover living mulch on weeds*

303 At wheat stem elongation, weed soil coverage in wheat pure crops was generally higher in organic
304 compared with conventional cropping systems at wheat stem elongation (on average 16.4 vs. 11.2
305 % of soil coverage, Table 2). However, the weed soil coverage in the intercropped wheat was
306 generally lower than in the pure wheat crop (on average 8 vs. 13 % of soil coverage, respectively).
307 The results on change in weed biomass between the intercropped and pure wheat at subclover
308 flowering varied significantly among the various agro-environmental zones (Fig. 8a). In the
309 Mediterranean North, the subclover strongly reduced the weed aboveground biomass by

310 approximately 53% in intercropped wheat compared to pure wheat where no weed control was
311 performed (data not shown). There was a significant negative relationship between the change in
312 weed aboveground biomass comparing intercropped to pure wheat treatments and the subclover
313 aboveground biomass (Fig. 7b). Moreover, a great reduction of weed aboveground biomass was
314 achieved with low N input (Fig. 8b), as subclover biomass was negatively affected by higher N
315 inputs (Fig 3).

316

317 **DISCUSSION**

318 *Development of wheat and subclover*

319 In all agro-environmental zones the intercropped wheat emerged before subclover and its early
320 growth was faster than the living mulch (data not shown). The slow initial development of the
321 legume compared to the cereal could be partly due to the establishment of costly nodulation in
322 terms of energy and nutrient requirements (Leung and Bonomley, 1994). Although subclover
323 emerged regularly after sowing in autumn in all sites, it did not survive the winter season in the
324 Atlantic North (KU), therefore no seeds and little biomass were produced. In Atlantic North
325 conditions, winter survival of subclover is severely threatened due to the low winter temperatures
326 (Brandsæter et al., 2002). However, in cold environments like Atlantic North, the poor winter
327 survival of subclover could be improved by anticipating the sowing time of the legume and sowing
328 the wheat into the clover via strip-tillage. In fact, according to the findings of Brandsæter et al.
329 (2008), early sowing could positively affect the winter survival rates of subclover. Moreover,
330 subclover genotypes more cold-tolerant than the cv. Campeda, which was adopted in this study,
331 should be evaluated, even if there is little information about cold tolerance of different subclover
332 cultivars (Teixeira et al., 2015; OSCAR, 2016). At the beginning of wheat stem elongation, the
333 cereal was much more efficient than subclover in terms of light absorption, due to its earlier growth
334 and greater leaf development throughout the winter period when temperatures were probably too
335 low for subclover development. However, total soil coverage in the wheat-subclover intercrops was
336 always higher than pure wheat in all sites. The higher total soil coverage in the intercropped crops
337 as a whole (wheat + subclover) compared to pure wheat is desirable as it reduces the risk of soil
338 erosion (Lithourgidis, 2011), it can reduce weed cover (Thorsted et al., 2006), and it increases light
339 interception and therefore biomass accumulation (Agegnehu et al., 2008). In particular, at
340 UNITUS, TUM and AGS, soil coverage of the subclover was much higher than that observed in the
341 other sites, while wheat soil coverage when intercropped with subclover was lower compared to the
342 pure wheat crop (Table 2). At these sites, wheat density was reduced by 1/3 in the intercropping
343 treatments. The subclover sowing arrangement was also very close to the wheat plants and this

344 could have led to increased competition between both species starting from early growth stages
345 (Thorsted et al., 2006).

346

347 *Subclover biomass production and its characteristics*

348 The subclover biomass production was very variable depending on different agro-environmental
349 zones. At subclover flowering, the highest amount of subclover aboveground biomass was observed
350 at UNITUS proving that this legume adapts well to the climatic conditions of the Mediterranean
351 North zone. Under these conditions, the subclover was able to produce a high amount of
352 aboveground biomass and mature seeds, which regenerated abundantly in the following autumn. In
353 the Continental zone (AGS and TUM) the legume grew regularly in the early phenological stages,
354 but at flowering the amount of aboveground biomass production was low (Fig. 3) probably due to
355 the cold temperatures at these sites during winter when air temperatures dropped below 0 °C several
356 times in January and February (Fig 1). Consequently, at TUM and AGS subclover reseedling was
357 very poor the following autumn (less than 20 seedlings m⁻²) suggesting that few subclover plants
358 survived after winter and were able to produce mature seeds. However, in these sites the subclover
359 provided more soil coverage than the omitted wheat row did in the controls and apparently
360 competed with the wheat. In fact, the wheat grain yield was significantly lower in intercropped
361 wheat than in pure stands at AGS, TUM and especially at UNITUS. In these sites, competition and
362 lower wheat seeding rates (-33% compared to pure wheat) probably contributed to this outcome.
363 The sowing density of intercropped species was achieved through a substitution series (Kelty and
364 Cameron, 1995) and the wheat seed density was probably too low to ensure a satisfactory density of
365 plants and consequently of fertile spikes. In fact, the decrease in grain yield, in intercropped wheat
366 compared to the pure wheat, was mainly due to fewer fertile spikes per surface area, which proved
367 to be the grain yield component most affected by changes in stand density in wheat according to
368 Blaser et al. (2006). Furthermore, the low plant density of the wheat probably reduced its
369 competitive ability, especially at UNITUS which showed the highest wheat yield gap in
370 intercropped wheat compared to pure wheat, as well as the highest aboveground biomass of
371 subclover (Fig. 3). By adopting an additive design, same wheat seed density used in both pure and
372 intercropped wheat (Kelty and Cameron, 1995), as in the case at the INRA and ICARDA sites, it
373 may be possible to reduce or eliminate the grain yield gap in intercropped wheat compared to pure
374 wheat. This would ensure a reliable wheat grain yield under pedo-climatic conditions where the
375 survival and establishment of subclover is uncertain, such as those observed at KU and ICARDA.
376 In general, increasing wheat seed density improves the competitive ability of the cereal, as well as
377 the number of wheat plants and fertile spikes (Weiner et al. 2010). Therefore, it is reasonable to

378 assume that similar effects could be obtained when the wheat is cultivated with clover living mulch
379 (Hiltbrunner et al., 2007b). This was confirmed for the TUM site and to some degree at UNITUS by
380 several experiments, where maintaining narrow rows of wheat usually resulted in the best grain
381 yields when intercropped with subclover (OSCAR, 2016).

382

383 *Wheat grain yield and yield components*

384 As expected, there were no effects of the cropping system at KU as (i) the wheat seed rate was
385 similar in both cropping systems, (ii) the amount of available N was probably too low to meet wheat
386 requirements, (iii) the subclover failed, which meant that there was no competition between the
387 intercropped species. Likewise no yield differences were observed at INRA and ICARDA where
388 the same seeding rates had been applied in both systems and the clover performed poorly.
389 Therefore, it seems that appropriate densities must be determined in accordance with local climatic
390 conditions in order to ensure adequate growth of both intercropped species.

391 Generally, nitrogen fertilization had e positive effects on wheat grain yield and yield components,
392 even if the effects was more consistent in pure wheat than in the intercropped wheat. In fact, the
393 potential of intercropping as a means of increasing the contribution of nitrogen obtained from
394 biological fixation seems to decrease with increases in the nitrogen fertilization level (Andersen et
395 al., 2005). This is supported by the fact that the subclover tended to be negatively affected by the
396 application of high mineral nitrogen doses (Fig. 3) and produced few seeds (data not shown), thus
397 decreasing its potential to deliver desired ecosystem services. Similar results were obtained in
398 previous studies, which investigated the effect of inorganic nitrogen availability on the behavior of
399 various winter cereal–legume intercropping systems (Gaudin et al., 2014). Thus, low input systems
400 seem to benefit more when subclover is used as living mulch in wheat in terms of subclover
401 biomass accumulation (Fig. 3). Moreover, Wittwer et al. (2017) showed that the benefits from cover
402 crops, as ecological management practice, are best acknowledged when management intensity is
403 reduced. Unlike the nitrogen fertilization, no significant changes in wheat grain yield were observed
404 following the compost application at KU (Table 3). This could be due to the low availability of
405 mineral nitrogen considering that the yard waste compost applied to the wheat was 90 and 75 kg ha⁻¹
406 of N with C:N ratios of 16 and 26, in 2012 and 2013, respectively. Probably only a part of these
407 amounts was available during the wheat cultivation period due to the slow release of mineral
408 nitrogen from yard waste compost, especially in cold climates like that of the Atlantic North (Laber,
409 2002).

410

411 *Effects of subclover living mulch on weeds*

412 The presence of subclover always reduced weed infestation in intercropped wheat compared to
413 wheat pure crop, even if the weed soil coverage in wheat pure crops was higher in organic
414 compared with conventional cropping systems. This is in agreement with several studies that
415 reported a higher presence of weeds in organic than in conventional cropping systems (Campiglia et
416 al., 2015; Halde et al., 2015). However, the reduction of weed soil coverage observed at all sites
417 indicates that subclover can contribute to weed management in intercropping systems, although
418 Campiglia et al. (2014) found that subclover was not a good competitor against weeds due to its low
419 growth rate. Nevertheless, the results on change in weed biomass between the intercropped and pure
420 wheat varied significantly among the various agro-environmental zones (Fig. 8a), thus reflecting
421 site-specific subclover performances. The potential suppressive effect on weeds was particularly
422 evident and could be demonstrated in the Mediterranean North, where subclover reduced weed
423 aboveground biomass by approximately 53% in intercropped wheat compared to pure wheat where
424 no weed control was performed (data not shown). In this environment, the subclover could establish
425 and grow properly and produced a high aboveground biomass. Contrastingly, although weed cover
426 was reduced at wheat stem elongation, weed biomass was much higher in the intercropped
427 treatments at AGS where herbicides were applied to control the weeds in the pure wheat. Thus,
428 weed competition by subclover was insufficient and may not be enough to fully replace herbicide
429 applications.

430 However, some weed reduction was even observed in environments where there was a shortage of
431 subclover at flowering with a significant effect at INRA (Table 2). Perhaps in these agro-
432 environments, the subclover had a negative effect on weed establishment in autumn and after it
433 withered, the aboveground biomass, which remained on the soil surface, may have acted as organic
434 dead mulch. Under these conditions, the cereal-legume association may fill more than one
435 ecological niche and may therefore contribute to suppressing a greater number of weed species with
436 different ecological requirements (Anil et al., 1998). This can be considered an important aspect
437 associated with using subclover as living mulch in wheat in environments where the subclover can
438 only survive for part of the cropping cycle and therefore cannot self-reseed. Indeed, it is evident that
439 low nitrogen input reduces weed biomass better than high nitrogen input, as subclover biomass is
440 increased and less nutrient are available for weeds to grow (Blackshaw, 2004). As already
441 highlighted for wheat grain yield production and subclover biomass accumulation, intercropping
442 wheat and subclover seems to be a suitable strategy in low input systems for controlling weeds as
443 well.

444

445 **CONCLUSION**

446 Overall, the research presented in this manuscript based on field experiments in different agro-
447 environmental conditions suggests that subclover used as living mulch in wheat can have positive
448 effects on wheat based cropping system performance. However, although the presence of subclover
449 generally reduced weed infestation, wheat was grown at a lower density than in the pure stand when
450 intercropped with subclover and yielded on average 6 % less than pure wheat, even if there were
451 significant differences depending on the environment and crop management system. It seems that
452 reducing the sowing density of wheat may not be the best option when it is intercropped with
453 subclover. In most experiments, the grain yield reduction was determined by a low number of fertile
454 spikes and occasionally by a reduction of the thousand grain weight. However, it was evident that
455 there was a negative relationship between subclover development and grain yield production in
456 intercropped wheat. In fact, when the subclover living mulch grew in favorable climatic conditions,
457 as in Mediterranean North (UNITUS), it caused the highest grain yield losses of up to 18%
458 compared to pure wheat. However, using appropriate management practices can reduce or eliminate
459 the yield gap between intercropped and pure wheat. In particular, when subclover is used as living
460 mulch in wheat our findings suggest that it is preferable: (i) to adopt similar seed density in
461 intercropped and in pure wheat to avoid a reduction of fertile spikes; (ii) to find an appropriate
462 spatial arrangement of the legume and cereal to reduce possible competitive effects between the two
463 species; (iii) to reduce the amount of nitrogen fertilizer administered. Therefore, using subclover as
464 living mulch in wheat is a feasible practice that is principally suitable for low input cropping
465 systems, although appropriate crop management practices should be developed in accordance with
466 local environmental conditions in order to avoid wheat yield loss.

467

468 **ACKNOWLEDGMENT**

469 This study was financed by the European Union FP7 Project n. 289277: OSCAR (Optimizing
470 Subsidiary Crop Applications in Rotations).

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Tables and figures

Table 1. Site details for the joint field trials carried out during 2012 – 2014 in Germany, Swiss, Italy, and Morocco representing Central north European temperate, Central south European temperate, Mediterranean Europe, Mediterranean Africa. AI = Aridity Index (De Martonne, 1926).

Agro-environmental zone	Atlantic North	----- Continental -----		Med. North	----- Med.South -----		
Country	Germany	Germany		Switzerland	Italy	Morocco	
Site	Neu-Eichenberg	----- Freising -----		Tänikon	Viterbo	Sidi Alla Tazi	Sidi El Aidi
Acronym	KU	TUMconv	TUMorg	AGS	UNITUS	INRA	ICARDA
Location	51°22' N 9°54' E 237 m a.s.l.	48°23' N 11°41' E 640 m a.s.l.	48°58' N 11°57' E 445 m a.s.l.	47°29' N 8°54' E 537 m a.s.l.	42°25' N 12°04' E 310 m a.s.l.	33°31' N 6°22' E 11 m a.s.l.	33°07' N 7°37' E 240 m a.s.l.
Clay (< 2 µm, g kg ⁻¹ of dry soil)	133	665	630	210	190	208	510
Silt (2-60 µm, g kg ⁻¹ of dry soil)	834	205	212	350	215	360	280
Sand (60-2000 µm, g kg ⁻¹ of dry soil)	33	130	158	440	595	146	210
Soil pH	6.2	6.5	6.5	7.3	6.7	7.11	8.3
Soil organic matter (mg C kg ⁻¹)	2.0	13.7	16.8	20.8	13.1	15.5	15.6
Soil nitrogen (mg N kg ⁻¹)	1.7	1.5	1.5	1.8	1.7	1.2	1.2
Average annual Temperature (°C)	8.9	7.5	7.8	8.7	14.1	20.0	19.2
Annual rainfall (mm)	698	800	786	1184	760	260	180
AI and classification	36.9 Wet	45.7 Wet	44.2 Wet	63.3 Very wet	31.5 Mildly wet	8.7 Semi dry	6.2 Semi dry

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587 **Table 2.** Soil coverage of wheat in both pure and intercropped stands, subclover in the intercropped
 588 stands and weeds, in both pure and intercropped stands, measured at the beginning of wheat stem
 589 elongation. Values belonging to the same variable followed by the same letter in rows for cropping
 590 systems (upper case letter) and in columns for site (lower case letter) are not significantly different
 591 (LSD P<0.05).
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Site	Soil coverage component (%) at stem elongation of wheat					
	Wheat		Subclover	Weeds		
	Pure	Intercropped		Pure	Intercropped	
KU	48.6 cA	47.8 bcA	3.2 c	16.1 aA	12.9 aA	
AGS	53.8 bA	50.2 abB	14.0 b	11.4 bcA	6.4 bB	
TUMorg	49.1 cA	42.6 cB	9.0 bc	16.6 aA	10.5 aB	
TUMconv	56.2 aA	53.3 aB	9.1 bc	10.6 bcA	5.8 bcB	
UNITUS	58.4 aA	49.5 bB	20.2 a	9.7 cA	2.4 cB	
INRA	50.4 bcA	49.2 bA	5.1 c	13.1 bA	6.7 bB	
ICARDA	47.7 cA	45.8 cA	0.6 c	13.3 bA	9.9 aA	

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597 **Table 3.** F-value of analysis of variance of wheat yield and yield components at the different sites.
 598 Straw (g DM m⁻²), grain yield (g DM m⁻²), fertile spikes m⁻², kernels spike⁻¹ (*, **, ***, significant
 599 at P ≤ 0.05, P ≤ 0.01, P ≤ 0.001, respectively). *D.f.* = Degree of freedom.

	<i>d.f.</i>	Straw	Yield	Spike	Kernel	TGW
TUMconv						
Cropping System (CS)	1	0.2136***	0.0466***	0.0003***	0.0012***	0.9492***
Fertilization (F)	1	0.0052***	0.0031***	0.6140***	0.8014***	0.8823***
CS x F	1	0.1737***	0.0070***	0.3376***	0.3496***	0.7717***
Year (Y)	1	0.0028***	0.0002***	0.3101***	0.5274***	0.9272***
No significant interactions						
TUMorg						
Cropping System (CS)	1	0.9398***	0.0435***	0.0205***	0.0481***	0.9543***
Year (Y)	1	0.0214***	0.0068***	0.3708***	0.0496***	0.0490***
CS x Y	1	0.3271***	0.6261***	0.6073***	0.7639***	0.9434***
KU						
Cropping System (CS)	1	0.4439***	0.7484***	0.8206***	0.6222***	0.8360***
Soil tillage (ST)	2	0.0012***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.6245***	0.0010***
CS x ST	2	0.9586***	0.4974***	0.8627***	0.9867***	0.9620***
Compost Fert. (F)	1	0.0973***	0.0852***	0.1827***	0.4729**	0.1426***
CS x F	1	0.5084***	0.8431***	0.6160***	0.4599**	0.5346***
ST x F	2	0.0491***	0.2843***	0.3968***	0.8474***	0.0664***
CS x ST x F	2	0.1295***	0.7729***	0.4103***	0.6959***	0.1983***
Year (Y)	1	0.0475***	0.0308***	0.0064***	0.0047***	0.0001***
Y x CS	1	0.0010***	0.8108***	0.4316***	0.5843***	0.5956***
Y x ST	2	0.3912***	0.0060***	0.3676***	0.2243***	0.0001***
AGS						
Cropping System (CS)	1	--	0.0001***	0.0013***	0.1552***	0.4797***
Fertilization (F)	1	--	0.0001***	0.0010***	0.0007***	0.0333***
CS x F	1	--	0.3163***	0.8054***	0.8140***	0.5490***
Year (Y)	1	--	0.0012***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0057***
CS x Y	1	--	0.8598***	0.0084***	0.0002***	0.1171***
F x Y	1	--	0.3686***	0.0831***	0.5945***	0.0009***
UNITUS						
Cropping System (CS)	1	0.0033***	0.0098***	0.9982***	0.0291***	0.1266***
Fertilization (F)	1	0.8243***	0.0457***	0.7513***	0.1144***	0.5813***
CS x F	1	0.8534***	0.2431***	0.7073***	0.0567***	0.4987***
Year (Y)	1	0.0002***	0.0001***	0.0008***	0.0494***	0.0001***
CS x Y	1	0.0080***	0.0028***	0.1579***	0.9922***	0.0100***
F x Y	1	0.8760***	0.0980***	0.8432***	0.7952***	0.2047***
INRA						
Cropping System (CS)	1	0.3834***	0.7685***	0.8806***	0.4328***	0.2576***
Fertilization (F)	1	0.2131***	0.0023***	0.0063***	0.0493***	0.9102***
CS x F	1	0.0829***	0.5019***	0.2616***	0.1770***	0.2345***
Year (Y)	1	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0278***	0.0424***
CS x Y	1	0.6536***	0.5832***	0.2364***	0.1295***	0.2720***
F x Y	1	0.1529***	0.0315***	0.0465***	0.0307***	0.0192***
ICARDA						
Cropping System (CS)	1	0.3659***	0.9869***	0.8191***	0.4858***	0.3020***
Fertilization (F)	1	0.4859***	0.9443***	0.0154***	0.0452***	0.9061***
CS x F	1	0.0747***	0.0240***	0.0075***	0.3725***	0.6483***
Year (Y)	1	0.0001***	0.0170***	0.0843***	0.0467***	0.1206***
No significant interactions						

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Figure 1. Weather conditions (monthly average of the daily temperatures and monthly total amount of rainfall) during the field experiments in 2012/2013 and 2013/2014 experimental years at the sites described in Table 1. Only one climate chart provided for the two sites at TUM as they were located near each other.

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Figure 2. Main crop stages of wheat and subclover in the conventional managed field during the experimental periods represented on a calendar scale. Developmental stages: SW = Sowing of wheat; WE = wheat emergence [Zadoks (Z) scale 10]; WT = Wheat tillering (Z20); FL Flag leaf (Z45); WF = Wheat flowering (Z65); WR = Wheat seed ripening (Z75); WH = Wheat harvesting (Z100); SS = Subclover sowing; SE = Subclover emergence; SF = Subclover flowering; SSR = Subclover seed ripening. N on X axis indicate fertilizer-N application.

Atlantic North

Continental

Med. North

Med. South

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649 **Figure 3.** Subclover aboveground biomass at subclover flowering in different nitrogen fertilization
 650 level. N+ = high N fertilization; N- = low N fertilization; N0 = no nitrogen fertilization; WC+ and
 651 WC- indicate treatments with and without application of compost at KU. Errors bars represent \pm
 652 standard errors.
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Figure 4. The main effects of cropping system on grain yield and yield component of wheat at different sites. Values belonging to the same variable followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to LSD (0.05). PW = Pure wheat; IW = Intercropped wheat; TGW = Thousand grain weight.

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666 **Figure 5.** Percentage change in wheat grain yield comparing (a) intercropped to pure wheat in
 667 different agro-environmental zones and (b) fertilization management. Data are grouped by
 668 Continental (AGS, TUMconv and TUMorg), Mediterranean North (UNITUS), Mediterranean South
 669 (INRA and ICARDA), High N Input and Low N input (AGS, TUMconv, UNITUS, INRA and
 670 ICARDA). Error bars are 95% confidence intervals. The number of observations is indicated in
 671 parentheses. Significant change is denoted by * (where error bars do not overlap zero).
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677 **Figure 6.** Percentage changes in wheat yield attributes comparing intercropped to pure wheat across
 678 different agro-environmental conditions and management agricultural practices. Error bars are 95%
 679 confidence intervals. The number of observations is indicated in parentheses. Significant changes
 680 are denoted by * (where error bars do not overlap zero).
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686 **Figure 7.** Relationship between the change in grain yield comparing intercropped to pure wheat and
687 the subclover aboveground biomass (a) and the change in weed aboveground biomass comparing
688 intercropped to pure wheat and the subclover aboveground biomass (b). The significance level is (*)
689 significant at $P \leq 0.05$.
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694 **Figure 8.** Percentage change in weed aboveground biomass comparing intercropped to pure wheat
 695 in different agro-environmental zones (a) and N fertilization level (b). Data used were those where
 696 the weeds were left to grow undisturbed. Data are grouped by Continental (TUMconv and
 697 TUMorg), Mediterranean North (UNITUS), Mediterranean South (INRA and ICARDA), High N
 698 Input and Low N input (TUMconv, UNITUS, INRA and ICARDA). Error bars are 95% confidence
 699 intervals. The number of observations is indicated in parentheses. Significant change is denoted by
 700 * (where error bars do not overlap zero).

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